

Corrigendum: The N400 Effect during Speaker-Switch—Towards a Conversational Approach of Measuring Neural Correlates of Language

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A corrigendum on

The N400 Effect during Speaker-Switch—Towards a Conversational Approach of Measuring Neural Correlates of Language

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In the original article, there was a mistake in **Figure 2 (B)** as published. The two right-sided difference topography visualizations (upper and lower) of the grand average of the N400 effect (incongruent minus congruent condition) for the two turn-taking modes were exchanged. The shown N400 effect plot for Listening is the N400 effect plot for Reading aloud, whereas the N400 effect plot shown for Reading aloud is the N400 effect plot for Listening. This only affects the visualization of the two difference topographies. The corrected **Figure 2** appears below. The authors apologize for this error and state that this does not change the scientific conclusions of the article in any way.

Conflict of Interest Statement: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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